

Interactions of Sevin, Diuron and *p*-Nitrophenol with Soils

M. ADHIKARI* and A. K. MANDAL

University College of Agriculture, University of Calcutta, 35, Ballygunge Circular Road, Calcutta-700 019

Manuscript received 29 January 1991, revised 14 October 1992, accepted 7 January 1993

The adsorption of sevin (insecticide) and diuron (herbicide) was studied on soils (untreated) and soils free of organic matter and sesquioxides. Freundlich equation was used to characterise the isotherms. Simple correlation analysis showed the significant influence of organic matter on the adsorption of sevin and diuron by untreated soils. In case of organic matter and oxide-free soils, adsorption was found to be correlated with clay content, specific surface area and Al_2O_3 content. It was observed that clay content of the soils (organic matter-free and oxide-free) accounts for a very large proportion of the variation in adsorption (K value). The higher adsorption of *p*-nitrophenol was noted in soils (untreated) having higher amount of sesquioxides. After removal of soluble salts from untreated soils, both sevin and diuron showed increase in adsorption. Exothermic nature of adsorption illustrated its temperature-dependence. Changes of soil pH caused decrease in adsorption. Evaluation of thermodynamic parameters indicates the physical nature of adsorption. The irreversible nature of adsorption process was revealed from desorption study.

The adsorption and desorption processes are important in determining the fate and effectiveness of pesticides in soil environment¹. Earlier reviews²⁻⁸ relating to adsorption of pesticides by soils and soil constituents show that the nature and extent of sorption depend upon the nature of soil constituents (including the water-soluble salts), pesticides and other environmental factors, like temperature, soil reaction and soil moisture. Previous studies on adsorption of diuron⁵ emphasised interactions of diuron with selected soils of West Bengal (other than the soils under investigation). Such studies emphasised mostly the importance of soil components, after careful isolation from soil, on retention of diuron. In the present study, the effects of organic matter, oxides, soluble salts (after removing each separately from untreated/original soil and interacting the residues with the pesticide solution) and pH on the adsorption of sevin (an insecticide, 1-naphthyl-*N*-methylcarbamate, water solubility 35 mg dm⁻³) and diuron (a herbicide, 3-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,1-dimethylurea, water solubility 42 mg dm⁻³), their desorption character and thermodynamic behaviour are reported to get more comprehensive information regarding nature of adsorption and role of soil separates on such adsorption.

For a proper evaluation of environmental hazards of pesticides applied to soil, the fate of their degradation products like aniline and its chlorinated derivatives, nitrophenols, naphthols were investigated⁹⁻¹². The present study also deals with the adsorption of *p*-nitrophenol, the most common bio-degradable product of methyl parathion, in soil environment.

Results and Discussion

The adsorption of sevin, diuron and *p*-nitrophenol by untreated, organic matter-free and oxide-

free soils was found to obey the Freundlich equation (eq. 1) over low concentration range,

$$(x/m) = KC_e^{1/n} \quad (1)$$

where, (x/m) is the amount adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent, C_e the equilibrium concentration of adsorbate in solution, K and n are constants dependent on nature of adsorbate, adsorbent and temperature of the system. A linear relation is obtained when $\log(x/m)$ is plotted against $\log C_e$ for each sample under the present investigation where slope and intercept provide values of $1/n$ and K respectively (Tables 1-3). The magnitude of K expresses the relative sorption capacity for the adsorbate¹³ for systems having comparable $1/n$ values and extent or degree of adsorption¹⁴. The value of $1/n$ provides an idea of intensity of adsorption¹⁵ which varies in regular manner with temperature of the system and with nature of the adsorbate¹⁶ for a given adsorbent.

The isotherms (Figs. 1-3) for sevin and diuron are close to S-type¹⁶. The nature of the isotherms indicates that sorption in soil is a complex phenomenon and shows the interactions of adsorbate (pesticides) with different types of adsorption sites having different surface energies¹⁷. The upward nature of curves indicates that after complete adsorption on adsorbent surface, the adsorbate molecules attract each other and associate on adsorbent surface. The isotherms for adsorption of *p*-nitrophenol on untreated soil show L-type curves (Fig. 4).

The values of K and $1/n$ are presented in Table 1 for different adsorbate-adsorbent interactions at different temperatures. The sequence of K values for adsorption of sevin and diuron on untreated soils is as follows: Mohitnagar > Kakdwip > Krishnagar > Purulia > Burdwan.

TABLE 1—FREUNDLICH CONSTANT (K AND $1/n$) FOR ADSORPTION OF SEVIN AND DIURON BY UNTREATED AND TREATED SOILS

Soil	Treatment	K ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)						$1/n$					
		Diuron			Sevin			Diuron			Sevin		
		33°	24°	10°	33°	24°	10°	33°	24°	10°	33°	24°	10°
Burdwan	Untreated	5.62	7.94	15.8	5.01	7.07	14.1	0.36	0.34	0.29	0.60	0.56	0.51
	O.M.-free	5.01	7.07	8.91	4.46	6.30	8.91	0.36	0.35	0.35	0.56	0.54	0.50
	OX.-free	3.98	5.62	7.94	3.98	6.30	7.07	0.37	0.35	0.32	0.51	0.45	0.45
Kakdwip	Untreated	12.5	22.4	25.1	11.2	19.9	22.4	0.27	0.24	0.23	0.50	0.46	0.43
	O.M.-free	10.0	12.6	19.9	8.91	11.2	17.8	0.31	0.30	0.23	0.50	0.45	0.41
	OX.-free	7.07	8.91	12.6	7.07	8.91	12.6	0.33	0.32	0.30	0.48	0.47	0.45
Krishnagar	Untreated	7.96	10.0	17.8	7.94	10.0	17.8	0.33	0.32	0.29	0.55	0.50	0.44
	O.M.-free	7.07	10.0	15.8	7.07	8.91	14.1	0.35	0.31	0.28	0.52	0.52	0.45
	OX.-free	6.30	7.94	11.2	6.30	7.94	11.2	0.36	0.33	0.33	0.47	0.46	0.44
Mohitnagar	Untreated	17.8	22.4	31.6	15.8	19.9	28.2	0.30	0.28	0.22	0.44	0.42	0.39
	O.M.-free	6.30	10.0	14.1	6.30	7.94	14.1	0.36	0.29	0.27	0.53	0.50	0.46
	OX.-free	5.62	7.07	10.0	5.62	7.07	10.0	0.35	0.33	0.28	0.53	0.50	0.45
Purulia	Untreated	6.30	10.0	17.8	6.30	10.0	15.8	0.37	0.34	0.25	0.58	0.52	0.50
	O.M.-free	4.46	5.62	8.91	4.46	5.62	8.91	0.37	0.37	0.35	0.55	0.53	0.48
	OX.-free	3.98	5.01	7.07	3.98	5.01	7.07	0.34	0.33	0.30	0.56	0.52	0.50

TABLE 2—FREUNDLICH CONSTANTS FOR ADSORPTION OF *p*-NITROPHENOL BY SOIL AT 33°

Soil	K ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)	$1/n$
Burdwan	56.2	0.19
Kakdwip	15.8	0.25
Krishnagar	19.9	0.25
Mohitnagar	25.1	0.50
Purulia	39.8	0.23

TABLE 3—FREUNDLICH CONSTANTS FOR ADSORPTION OF DIURON AND SEVIN BY DIFFERENT TREATED SOILS AT 33°

Soil	Treatment	K ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)		$1/n$	
		Diuron	Sevin	Diuron	Sevin
Burdwan	pH 4	3.98	3.89	0.39	0.63
	pH 8	5.01	4.46	0.38	0.62
	Salt-free	6.30	6.30	0.35	0.61
Kakdwip	pH 4	8.91	7.94	0.28	0.56
	pH 8	11.2	10.0	0.27	0.55
	Salt-free	15.8	15.8	0.30	0.48
Krishnagar	pH 4	6.30	6.30	0.35	0.56
	pH 8	7.07	7.07	0.36	0.53
	Salt-free	11.2	7.94	0.31	0.55
Mohitnagar	pH 4	10.0	10.0	0.33	0.50
	pH 8	14.1	12.6	0.31	0.46
	Salt-free	19.9	17.8	0.30	0.45
Purulia	pH 4	4.46	4.46	0.40	0.62
	pH 8	5.62	5.62	0.35	0.60
	Salt-free	7.07	7.07	0.37	0.60

But the order of adsorption of sevin and diuron on organic matter-free and oxide-free soils is as follows: Kakdwip > Krishnagar > Mohitnagar > Burdwan > Purulia.

The higher adsorption by Mohitnagar soil (untreated) is due to its higher organic matter content, and high clay content of Kakdwip soil (O.M.-free/OX.-free) is responsible for its higher retention of pesticides in comparison to other soils. The K values are higher for diuron than for sevin for all the adsorbents studied. The untreated soils possess higher K values than the organic matter-free soils. The adsorption of pesticides in organic

Fig. 1. Isotherms for adsorption of sevin by Kakdwip soil at different temperatures (O) 33, (●) 24 and (▲) 10°.

matter-free soils is more than that in oxide-free soils. The difference between adsorption (K value) by untreated and organic matter-free soils is found to be much higher than that by the organic matter-free and oxide-free soils. This observation indicates higher influence of organic matter than that of oxides on adsorption of pesticides. Similar observation was noted in clay samples from earlier study. The K values (Table 3) are found to be higher in salt-free soils than in untreated soils. Similar report is available for adsorption of different pesticides in presence and absence of soluble salts in soils⁴.

The data (K values) obtained from adsorption of *p*-nitrophenol by different soils (Table 2) show that the adsorption capacity followed the sequence: Burdwan > Purulia > Mohitnagar > Krishnagar > Kakdwip

Fig. 2. Isotherms for adsorption of diuron by Mohitnagar soils at 33° : (O) untreated, (●) organic matter-free and (▲) oxide-free.

Fig. 3. Isotherms for adsorption of diuron by different treated soils at 33° : (O) pH 4, (●) pH 8 and (Δ) salt-free Mohitnagar soil.

The higher *K* values for Burdwan and Purulia soils indicate higher affinity of pesticide for mineral surfaces. Similar reports are available from earlier studies^{18,19}.

The values of $1/n$ are less than unity, and are higher for adsorption of sevin and diuron by organic matter- and oxide-free soils than those for adsorption by untreated soils (Tables 2 and 3).

Fig. 4. Isotherms for adsorption of *p*-nitrophenol by soils at 33° : (O) Burdwan, (▲) Kakdwip and (●) Krishnagar.

The physicochemical properties of the untreated, organic matter-free and oxide-free soils are correlated with the corresponding Freundlich *K* values (at 33°) for sevin, diuron and *p*-nitrophenol. Significant positive correlations are noted between *K* values and organic matter ($r \approx 0.968^{**}$ for diuron, $r \approx 0.940^*$ for sevin) content of the untreated soils. Similar relations are obtained between *K* value and clay content ($r \approx 0.987^{**}$ for diuron, $r \approx 0.987^{**}$ for sevin), Al_2O_3 content ($r \approx 0.980^{**}$ for diuron and $r \approx 0.963^{**}$ for sevin) and specific surface area ($r \approx 0.921^*$ for diuron and $r \approx 0.921^*$ for sevin) of the organic matter-free soils. In case of the oxide-free soils significant relation is obtained between *K* values and clay content ($r \approx 0.989^*$

Fig. 5. Retention of diuron by Purulia soil : (●) adsorption and (O) desorption.

for diuron, $r \approx 0.898^*$ for sevin). No significant relation (r) was obtained between adsorption of *p*-nitrophenol and physicochemical properties of the untreated soils.

The above correlation analyses were unable to predict the relative contributions of soil components on the adsorption of pesticides by untreated soils. For this, step(up)-wise regression analysis²⁰ was attempted.

The first step shows the relationships between K values (at 33°) and percentage organic matter (O.M.) or percentage clay content (Cl), which yields higher R^2 value, i.e. higher coefficient of determination, for interactions between untreated soil and pesticides (diuron, sevin and *p*-nitrophenol) which is stated as follows :

$$K_{\text{Diuron}} = 2.904 + 4.863 \text{ O.M.} \dots (R^2 = 0.9392) \quad (2)$$

(1.452)

$$K_{\text{Sevin}} = 3.196 + 4.134 \text{ O.M.} \dots (R^2 = 0.9401) \quad (3)$$

(1.224)

$$K_{\text{p-Nitrophenol}} = 48.130 - 0.644 \text{ Cl} \dots (R^2 = 0.5612) \quad (4)$$

(12.688)

It is observed from the values of R^2 that 93.92, 94.01 and 56.12% variations of K values are explained by organic matter (eqs. 2 and 3) and clay (eq. 4) for adsorption of diuron, sevin and *p*-nitrophenol respectively. The second step of the regression analysis involves additions of percentage aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3), percentage clay and percentage iron oxide (Fe_2O_3) content with organic matter and clay content (eqs. 2–4) as the second independent variable and is expressed as

$$K_{\text{Diuron}} = 1.845 + 4.721 \text{ O.M.} + 0.864 \text{ Al}_2\text{O}_3 \dots$$

(0.118) (0.083)

($R^2 = 0.9989$) (5)

$$K_{\text{Sevin}} = 2.152 + 3.870 \text{ O.M.} + 0.055 \text{ Cl} \dots$$

(0.189) (0.009)

($R^2 = 0.9963$) (6)

$$K_{\text{p-n/Nitrophenol}} = 31.266 - 0.568 \text{ Cl} + 95.750 \text{ Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \dots$$

(0.185) (35.139)

($R^2 = 0.9084$) (7)

The comparison of R^2 values as obtained from eqs. (2)–(4) with those obtained from eqs. (5)–(7) reveals the relative contributions of Al_2O_3 , clay and Fe_2O_3 by 6.97, 5.62 and 34.92% on variability of K values for adsorptions of diuron, sevin and *p*-nitrophenol respectively. Similar relations are obtained after addition of Fe_2O_3 with eqs. (5) and (6) and organic matter with eq. (7) and the relationships are expressed as

$$K_{\text{Diuron}} = 0.178 + 4.872 \text{ O.M.} + 0.8485 \text{ Al}_2\text{O}_3$$

(0.151) (0.0712)

$$+ 1.999 \text{ Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \dots (R^2 = 0.9996) \quad (8)$$

(1.499)

$$K_{\text{Sev}} = 2.310 + 3.825 \text{ O.M.} + 0.055 \text{ Cl}$$

(0.368) (0.013)

$$- 0.604 \text{ Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \dots (R^2 = 0.9967) \quad (9)$$

(3.642)

$$K_{\text{p-Nitrophenol}} = 19.485 - 0.607 \text{ Cl} + 132.456 \text{ Fe}_2\text{O}_3$$

(92.696) (59.868)¹

$$+ 0.185 \text{ OM} \dots (R^2 = 0.9488) \quad (10)$$

(5.737)

It is observed from the above relations (eqs. 2–10) that organic matter plays a major role in the retention of diuron and sevin. Contrarily, inorganic constituents exceed the influence of organic components for the adsorption of *p*-nitrophenol. It may occur possibly due to higher affinities of active functional groups of sevin and diuron for polar functional groups at organic matter surface and of *p*-nitrophenol for charged inorganic molecules and clay surface of untreated soil. Similar analysis reveals that clay content explains 98.14 and 92.31, and 90.31 and 82.95% variations of adsorption of diuron and sevin by organic matter-free and oxide-free soils respectively. The above mentioned data distinguish the relative participation of organic and inorganic constituents on adsorption of pesticides by soils^{17,21–24}.

The influence of pH on adsorption of pesticides by soil is noticed after adjusting the soil pH at 4 and 8 respectively. The K and $1/n$ values obtained from the graphical plots (Fig. 3) of Freundlich equation (eq. 1) are given in Table 3. It appears that K values increase with decreasing acidity. Such results indicate that an increasing competition prevails between pesticide molecules and the added H^+/Na^+ ions for adsorption sites on adsorbent surface. Similar results are obtained from the earlier studies²⁵.

The K and $1/n$ values for adsorption of different pesticides at different temperatures (33, 24 and 10°) are presented in Table 1. An increase in temperature resulted in a decrease in adsorption (K values) indicating exothermic nature of the adsorption processes²⁶. The $1/n$ values are found to decrease with the decrease of temperatures²⁷.

The desorption patterns of sevin and diuron (Fig. 3) are evaluated from percent desorption values (Table 4). The decreasing sequence for desorption of sevin and diuron from untreated soils is as follows : Burdwan > Purulia > Krishnagar > Kakdwip > Mohitnagar.

The above findings indicate an inverse relation between desorption of sevin or diuron with soil organic matter content. Similar results were found in earlier studies of desorption of diuron from sediment samples²⁷.

The changes in the standard free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) were evaluated from the adsorption data²⁸ at 33, 24 and 10° using equations (11), (12) and (13),

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_0 \quad (11)$$

$$\ln \frac{K_0^2}{K_0^1} = -\frac{\Delta H^\circ}{R} \left[\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1} \right] \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta S^\circ = \frac{\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ}{T} \quad (13)$$

K_0 for the adsorption is defined as²⁸

$$K_0 = \frac{a_s}{a_e} = \frac{\gamma_s C_s}{\gamma_e C_e} \quad (14)$$

where, a_s is the activity of the adsorbed solute, a_e the activity of the solute in the equilibrium

solution, C_s the μg of solute adsorbed per ml of solvent in contact with the adsorbent surface, C_e the μg of solute per ml of solvent in equilibrium solution, γ_s the activity coefficient of the adsorbed solute, and γ_e the activity coefficient of the solute in the equilibrium solution. C_s was calculated according to the equation²⁹,

$$C_s = \frac{(\rho_1/M_1)A_1}{\frac{s}{N(x/m)} - \frac{A_2}{M_2 \times 10^6}} \quad (15)$$

where, ρ_1 , M_1 , M_2 , A_1 and A_2 are respectively, the density (g ml^{-1}), molecular weight (g mol^{-1}) and cross-sectional area ($\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of the solvent and solute molecules, s is the specific surface area of the adsorbent and (x/m) the amount of adsorption per g of adsorbent expressed as $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ and N the Avogadro number. The cross-sectional area of the solvent (A_1) and solute (A_2) molecules were estimated from the equation³⁰,

$$A = 1.091 \times 10^{-16} \left[\frac{M \times 10^{24}}{N\rho} \right]^{2/3} \quad (16)$$

where, M and ρ are, respectively, the molecular weight and the density of the solvent or solute. The condition that

$$\frac{s}{N(x/m)} > \frac{A_2}{M_2 \times 10^6} \quad (17)$$

was met by all the experiments in this report. Thus equation (6) is reduced to (16)

$$C_s = \frac{(\rho_1/M_1)A_1}{\frac{s}{N(x/m)}} \quad (18)$$

Table 5 shows that (ΔG°) values are small and negative for all the adsorbate-adsorbent interactions. It varies from -14 to -16 kJ mol^{-1} and increases, in most cases, with decrease of temperature, indicating spontaneous nature of the adsorption processes. Similar results were available from

TABLE 4—DESORPTION OF ADSORBED DIURON AND SEVIN FROM SOILS

Soil	Diuron					Sevin					
Burdwan											
Adsorption (%)	30	35	36	40	42	20	25	26	30	32	33
Desorption (%)											
1st	33	28	24	21	20	25	20	25	25	25	25
2nd	33	27	24	20	20	27	20	20	22	21	20
3rd	25	27	21	17	19	18	16	17	17	21	21
Kakdwip											
Adsorption (%)	30	40	43	45	48	30	35	36	40	40	40
Desorption (%)											
1st	28	21	19	19	17	20	17	18	19	20	21
2nd	31	26	16	17	17	17	17	17	19	19	18
3rd	30	20	15	14	15	10	17	13	14	15	16
Krishnagar											
Adsorption (%)	30	40	46	45	46	30	30	33	35	36	37
Desorption (%)											
1st	44	25	18	19	18	17	17	20	21	22	23
2nd	60	28	15	11	18	16	16	19	23	22	21
3rd	50	15	10	10	16	10	14	15	18	18	19
Mohitnagar											
Adsorption (%)	40	45	50	50	52	30	35	40	40	42	42
Desorption (%)											
1st	33	22	17	17	16	20	14	17	19	19	20
2nd	37	24	16	15	15	21	13	15	19	18	18
3rd	40	19	13	12	14	21	12	12	14	14	15
Purulia											
Adsorption (%)	30	35	40	42	44	30	30	33	32	34	33
Desorption (%)											
1st	28	24	21	23	19	17	17	20	23	24	25
2nd	31	25	21	18	19	16	16	19	20	19	20
3rd	22	25	22	18	23	10	14	15	19	19	21

TABLE 5—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS ASSOCIATED WITH ADSORPTION OF SEVIN AND DIURON BY SOILS

Soil	Temp. °C	$10^{-3} K_0$		$\Delta G^\circ \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$		$\Delta H^\circ \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$		$\Delta S^\circ \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	
		Diuron	Sevin	Diuron	Sevin	Diuron	Sevin	Diuron	Sevin
Burdwan	33	5.44	3.65	-16.17	-15.16	-12.14	-9.36	13.23	18.94
	24	6.02	4.03	-15.96	-14.95				
	10	8.12	4.93	-15.92	-14.74				
Kakdwip	33	3.65	2.99	-15.16	-14.66	-16.38	-12.13	-3.82	13.81
	24	4.61	3.65	-15.28	-14.70				
	10	6.02	4.03	-15.20	-14.28				
Krishnagar	33	4.46	2.99	-15.66	-14.65	-14.36	-10.46	4.49	13.82
	24	6.02	3.65	-15.96	-14.70				
	10	6.65	4.63	-15.45	-14.28				
Mohitnagar	33	5.44	4.03	-16.17	-15.41	-21.04	-13.27	-15.54	7.01
	24	8.12	4.93	-16.72	-15.45				
	10	9.92	6.02	-16.38	-15.20				
Purulia	33	6.65	4.93	-16.72	-15.92	-13.23	-9.32	11.42	21.59
	24	8.12	5.44	-16.72	-15.71				
	10	9.92	6.65	-16.38	-15.45				

TABLE 6—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL DATA OF UNTREATED AND TREATED SOILS*

Soil	Organic matter %	Mechanical composition %			Free oxides %		EC_e dS m ⁻¹	Cation exchange capacity [cmol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]						Specific surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)		
		Sand	Silt	Clay	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃		pH (1 : 2.5)			Un-treated	O.M.-free	OX.-free	Un-treated	O.M.-free	OX.-free
								Un-treated	O.M.-free	OX.-free						
Burdwan	0.65	63.73	22.46	13.16	0.28	0.81	0.17	5.8	4.3	9.4	15.1	10.0	27.5	77	63	25
Kakdwip	1.52	4.13	36.57	57.74	0.19	3.90	1.74	6.6	5.4	8.2	21.4	22.5	30.5	135	103	35
Krishnagar	1.07	61.03	12.47	26.50	0.07	1.53	0.34	6.5	4.8	9.0	18.5	18.2	28.5	109	77	29
Mohitnagar	3.19	49.90	25.50	24.60	0.03	1.04	0.19	5.1	5.2	8.1	16.2	14.3	27.7	103	64	26
Purulia	0.89	79.6	11.50	8.22	0.20	0.09	0.06	5.6	8.4	8.8	13.6	5.0	24.3	70	38	19

*O.M.-free=organic matter-free soils ; OX.-free=oxide free-soils.

earlier studies²³. The values of ΔH° are small and negative indicating physical type of adsorption⁵. The values of ΔS° lie between -3.82 and -15.54 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹. Such low values suggest that the adsorbate molecules are somewhat ordered on the adsorbent surface. Similar results were obtained from earlier studies^{5, 19, 23}. The deviations from such molecular association are indicated by the positive values of ΔS° . Similar evidence was obtained from earlier studies³¹.

Experimental

Soil samples (0–20 cm) were collected from different State Agricultural farms of West Bengal, viz. Burdwan (Inceptisol), Kakdwip (Entisol), Krishnagar (Inceptisol), Mohitnagar (Entisol) and Purulia (Alfisol). The organic matter and oxides were removed by treatment with hydrogen peroxide and mixture of sodium citrate-bicarbonate-dithionite³². The soils were leached repeatedly with distilled water until negligible EC_e was attained. pH of each soil (untreated) was adjusted to 4 and 8 by dilute HCl (N)/dilute NaOH(N) followed by incubation and leaching with distilled water and alcohol.

Among the physicochemical properties (Table 6), the mechanical composition, pH (1 : 2.5), electrical conductance (EC_e) of saturation extract, organic matter content, cation exchange capacity³³, free oxides³² and specific surface area³² of untreated, organic matter-free and oxide-free soils were determined following standard procedures.

For adsorption experiments, a known amount (1 g) of each adsorbent (soil-untreated, soil-organic matter-free, soil-oxide-free, soil-salts-free, soils at pH 4 and 8) was taken in screw-capped centrifuge tubes and shaken for a maximum of 12 h with aqueous solutions (20 ml) of sevin (sevin 50 WP, containing 50% carbaryl; Union Carbide), diuron (technical grade product containing 98.5% diuron produced by Agromore Ltd.) and *p*-nitrophenol (A.R.) in the concentration range 1–30 ppm in a thermostat at 33, 24 and 10° ($\pm 1^\circ$), respectively. Preliminary kinetic studies confirmed the attainment of equilibrium within 12 h for adsorption of different pesticides by soils. After equilibration, samples were removed and centrifuged. The supernatant (10 ml) (for sevin and diuron as adsorbate

and untreated soil as adsorbent) from each tube was withdrawn and replaced by equal volume of 0.1 N KCl for subsequent desorption experiment at 33°. This procedure was repeated in each set for three desorption steps. The supernatants collected for adsorption and desorption experiments were analysed colorimetrically for sevin³⁵, diuron³⁶ and *p*-nitrophenol³⁷ at 590, 555 and 420 nm, respectively, against suitable blank.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Directorate of Agriculture, Government of West Bengal, for financial assistance.

References

- G. W. BAILEY and J. L. WHITE, *Residue Rev.*, 1970, 29, 29.
- S. L. CHOPRA, N. DAS and B. DAS, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1970, 18, 437.
- F. J. STEVENSON, *J. Environ. Qual.*, 1972, 1, 333.
- S. L. CHOPRA, *Indian J. Agric. Chem.*, 1976, 9, 125.
- M. ADHIKARI, A. RAY and S. K. SANYAL, *Indian Agric.*, 1985, 29, 87.
- M. ADHIKARI and A. RAY, *Clay Res.*, 1987, 6, 101.
- J. KOZAK and J. B. WEBER, *Weed Sci.*, 1983, 31, 368.
- M. ADHIKARI and A. RAY, *Indian Agric.*, 1989, 33, 23.
- S. SALTZMAN and S. YARIV, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1975, 39, 474.
- R. VAN BLADEL and A. MOREALE, *J. Soil Sci.*, 1977, 28, 93.
- J. J. HHSSETT, W. L. BANWART, S. G. WOOD and J. C. MEANS, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 1981, 45, 38.
- W. H. BAARSCHERS, J. ELVISH and S. P. RYAN, *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*, 1983, 30, 621.
- A. W. ADAMSON, "Physical Chemistry of Surfaces", Interscience, New York, 1967, p. 398.
- R. HAQUE, "Environmental Dynamics of Pesticides", eds. R. HAQUE and V. H. FREED, Plenum Press, New York, 1975, p. 97.
- H. FREUNDLICH, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry", Methuen, London, 1926, p. 110.
- C. H. GILES, T. H. MC EWAN, S. N. NAKHWA and D. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3973.
- A. FELSOT and P. A. DAHM, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1979, 27, 557.
- P. M. HUANG, R. GROVER and R. B. MC KERCHER, *Soil Sci.*, 1984, 138, 20.
- M. ADHIKARI, A. K. MANDAL and A. RAY, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1991, 39, 680.
- G. W. SNEDECOR and W. G. COCHRAN, "Statistical Methods", Oxford & IBH, New Delhi, 1967.
- M. ADHIKARI, A. K. MANDAL, A. RAY and N. DAS, *Clay Res.*, 1991, 10, 52.
- P. A. WAHID and N. SETHUNATHAN, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1978, 28, 623.

23. W. B. MC CLOSKEY and D. E. BAYER, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 1987, **51**, 605.
24. G. D. CANCELA, E. R. TABODA and F. SÁNEHEZ-RASERO, *J. Soil Sci.*, 1992, **43**, 99.
25. J. P. SINGHAL and N. SINGH, *Soil Sci.*, 1978, **125**, 301.
26. R. VAN BLADEL and A. MOREALE, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1974, **38**, 244.
27. D. E. PECK, D. L. CORWIN and W. J. FARMER, *J. Environ. Qual.*, 1980, **9**, 101.
28. J. W. BIGGAR and M. W. CHEUNG, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1973, **37**, 863.
29. Y. FU, R. S. HANSEN and F. E. BARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1948, **52**, 374.
30. K. KODERA and Y. ONISHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1959, **32**, 356.
31. S. KHAN and N. Z. KHAN, *Clay Res.*, 1986, **5**, 82.
32. C. A. BLACK in "Methods of Soil Analysis", ed. C. A. BLACK, Vol 2, Am. Soc. Agron., Madison, 1965
33. M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Prentice-Hall of India, New Delhi, 1973.
34. D. C. CARTER, M. D. HEILMAN and C. C. GONZALEZ. *Soil Sci.*, 1965, **100**, 360.
35. G. ZWEIG, in "Analytical Methods for Pesticides, Plant Growth Regulations and Food Additives" ed. G. ZEWIG, Academic, New York, 1964, Vol. II.
36. G. KULSHRESTHA, *J. Assoc. Off. Anal. Chem.*, 1979, **62**, 1191.